

the graph at n values of 0.5 and 1.5 and are found to be 7.44 and 7.13 at 30° and 7.64 and 7.33 at 40° respectively.

Thermodynamic functions

The values of overall changes in the free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) on complex formation have been determined at 40° by employing standard equations⁵⁻⁶ described earlier and are -21.6 K.cal/mole, -17.3 K cal/mole and 14.0 Cal/mole/degree respectively

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Polarographic and Potentiometric investigations of Monochloro acetate complexes of Cd(II)

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THIS communication reports the investigations of Monochloro-acetate complexes both by the Polarographic and Potentiometric methods.

Experimental

The polarographic measurements were carried out with a manual Polarograph¹. The capillary constant determined at half wave potential of the system was found to be $1.60 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Saturated calomel electrode was employed as reference. The value of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ was found to be $28.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ m.v.}$ at 30°.

Potentiometric procedure was similar to that adopted by Riley². Cadmium metal rod about 6 m.m. in diameter and 10 c.m. in length was amalgamated by the procedure suggested by Meites and

Thomas³ and employed as indicator electrode. S.C.E. was again used as reference. All the Polarographic and Potentiometric investigations were carried out at constant temp. 30°. Sodium salt solutions of Monochloroacetic acid were used. The ligand concentration in the series of solutions was kept significantly lower than the ionic strength (2.0M) adjusted by adding Potassium nitrate.

Results and Discussion

The composition and the cumulative formation constants of the complexes $\beta_1 = K_1 \times K_2 \dots K_n$ (where $K_1, K_2, \dots$ are step-wise formation constants) were determined by Deford and Hume's⁴ method from Polarographic data and by Leden's⁵ method from Potentiometric data.

Table 1 lists the results of measurements and in Table 2 are given the over all formation constants (β_1) determined by polarographic and potentiometric methods.

TABLE 1—CADMIUM—MONOCHLOROACETATE

Cd(II) = 0.4 mM, Temp. = 30°, $\mu = 2.0$, pH = 4.55

[L]	Polarographic data		Potentiometric data
	i_d (μA)	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	E (v)
0.00	2.96	-0.5770	-0.6660
0.04	2.88	-0.5785	-0.6685
0.08	2.78	-0.5800	-0.6710
0.12	2.70	-0.5815	-0.6735
0.16	2.64	-0.5825	-0.6760
0.20	2.58	-0.5840	-0.6775
0.28	2.50	-0.5865	-0.6810
0.40	2.40	-0.5895	-0.6860
0.60	2.30	-0.5940	-0.6925
0.80	2.26	-0.5975	-0.6975
1.00	2.20	-0.6000	-0.7010

TABLE 2

Method of Investigation	β_1	β_2
Polarographic Method	3.90	4.10
Potentiometric Method	6.00	8.10

In the system investigated formation of two complexes $[\text{Cd}(\text{M.C.A.})]^+$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{M.C.A.})_2]^{0+}$ at ionic strength 2.0 and ligand concentration range 0-1.0M was indicated. Acetic acid is known to form four complexes with Cd(II)⁶, formation of lesser number of complexes in case of monochloroacetic acid ligand may be attributed to its poor complex forming capacity. As Cd(II) is supposed to coordinate with four water molecules in aqueous solution, the positions remaining short of those occupied by ligands may be supposed to be taken up by water molecules.

The values of stability constants depend to a great extent on the method of investigation, however, it is seen that β_1 values determined by both the methods of investigation are in close agreement.

The pK value of Monochloroacetic acid and Acetic acid are 2.86 and 4.767 respectively, thus substitution of chlorine decreases the protophilic property of Acetate ion and may therefore, be supposed to be the cause of lesser stability of M.C.A. complexes a compared with Acetate complexes.

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Self condensation of Homophthalic anhydride : Some New Findings*

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3-(2-CARBOXYBENZYL) isocoumarin (III) is reported to have been obtained by (i) refluxing homophthalic anhydride (I) with pyridine and piperidine¹, with quinoline² and with pyridine alone³, (ii) heating homophthalic acid and its anhydride with sodium or potassium acetates^{3,4} and (iii) by pyrolysis of ammonium homophthalate⁵. In the last reaction (III) was obtained as by-product together with homophthalimide that formed the major product.

It is now found that keeping (I) with pyridine alone at room temperature furnishes 4-carboxy-3-(2-carboxybenzyl)-isocoumarin (IV) as a stable substance in a yield exceeding 80%. It smoothly decarboxylates on heating in a metal both at 220° to

give (III). Treatment of (IV) with aq. NaOH in cold followed by acidification gave by decarboxylative hydrolysis the known acetone derivative (VI, R = H) that was earlier obtained by hydrolysis of (III).

Self condensation of (I) would give (II) by acylation (vide mechanism⁶ for acetylation of (I)). It is the rearrangement further of (II) that has given (IV). In the lit. cited above and so also when the present self condensation reaction was heated on boiling water bath, (III) and not (IV) was isolated. This was because the reaction conditions were such that they facilitated decarboxylation of the 4-carboxy group.

The isocoumarin (IV) unlike 4-acylisochromanones⁶ was found to be stable to conc. H₂SO₄, did not give colouration with alc. FeCl₃ and its eq. wt. by titration against aq. NaOH (0.01 N) at 0° showed it to be dibasic. Its possibility to be the isomeric (II) is thus ruled out.

Various reactions of the isocoumarin (III) and the ketone (VI) are already reported¹⁻⁵. The following are the additions. The isocoumarin (III) is found to give the ester (V) in good yield when it is refluxed with MeOH/conc. H₂SO₄ for 3 hr. The same reaction refluxed for 36 hr. is reported⁵ to have yielded a mixture of the ester (V) and the ketone (VII). The ketone (VI) is found to get reduced smoothly with NaBH₄ in methanol at room temperature to furnish, on acidification, 3-(2-carboxybenzyl)-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIII) in good yield. The reduction but at reflux temperature is reported⁴ to have furnished (IX).

Experimental

4-Carboxy-3-(2-carboxybenzyl) isocoumarin (IV): A mixture of homophthalic anhydride (I) (1 g.) and dry pyridine (35 ml.) was well stirred with a magnetic stirrer when it slowly formed a dark brown solution. After leaving it overnight at room temperature, it was poured over crushed ice and HCl. The solid that separated, crystallised from ethyl acetate (charcoal) as heavy plates m.p. 218° (decomp.) yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 67.0 and H, 4.1%. C₁₈H₁₂O₆ requires C, 66.7 and H, 3.7%); λ_{max}^{MeOH} 230, 275 and 325 nm (log ϵ 4.59, 4.15 and 3.76).

When the above reaction was heated on boiling water bath for 3 hr. and worked up as above, the isocoumarin (III) was obtained that crystallised from dilute methanol in silky needles m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic specimen¹ 206-7 (Lit.¹ m.p. 210°), yield 0.6 g.

Action of aq. NaOH on (IV): α , α' -Bis-(2-carboxybenzyl) acetone (VI): A solution of the isocoumarin (IV) (1 g.) in aq. NaOH (10 ml., 10%) was left aside at room temperature for half an hour and then acidified with HCl. The solid that separated on scratching (crude yield 0.9 g., m.p. 97-99°), crystallised from ethyl acetate (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic specimen⁵ prepared from (III) 199-200° (decomp.) (Lit. m.p.

* Part XII of the series Isocoumarins.